

ANALYSIS OF ALMOND INFLUENCE WITH PEACH BIT AND METHODS OF FIGHT AGAINST IT

Umurzakov Elmurod¹, Javliyev Sunnat²

¹ Professor, Department of Agrotechnology, Production Automation and Management, Samarkand Veterinary Medical Institute, Samarkand, Republic of Uzbekistan, ² Master, Named after Sharof Rashidov Samarkand State University.

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the contamination of almond tree with peach lice, pest control methods. Based on the analysis, scientific and practical conclusions were made.

Introduction. Peach lice (*Myzodes persicae* Sulz.) Seriously damage almonds. Plant lice are common and are sucking pests that greatly affect the yield and quality of almonds. The pest is an insect belonging to the subfamily Aphidinea of the family Homoptera. There are about three thousand of them. *Myzodes persicae* Sulz. - Peach lice are very common and at the same time very harmful species [1,2,3,4]. Research methods. Entomological calculations and observations Yaxontov, G.Ya. Bey-Bienko, A.A. Zaxvatkin, S.A. Murodov, the density of pests Sh.T. It was carried out on the basis of Khodjaev's methods [4]. The degree of insect damage was determined by V.I. Determined by the Tansky style.

The results of the analysis. Peach lice (*Myzodes persicae* Sulz.) Are the main pest of almonds and are distributed in all regions of the world. Lice absorb the juice of almond leaves and contaminate the leaves with sticky waste, residual peel

residue and dead skin, reducing fruit quality. Peach lice overwinter in the ovarian phase.

Females lay their eggs mainly on the trunks of young trees and on the bark of thick branches. Peach lice feed on a variety of plants, but plants that lay wintering eggs are the main food plant. In early spring, from the eggs laid on these plants, several joints of the lice that give birth live develop. Later, as the spring sap movement in the plants decreases, the lice migrate to other plants, i.e., intermediate plants. Peach lice do not pass from one plant to another until they have studied the living conditions in the plants they feed on. After being hit by a lot of peach lice, which greatly impairs the growth and development of the plants, the plants become unable to feed on these lice. As the number of lice increases and the plants become more aggressive, winged lice begin to emerge from the newborn larvae. When the microclimate, soil, etc. in the orchards are different, the living

conditions in these fields are also different. Under such conditions, wingless lice also crawl from one plant to another. Ants are typical companions that feed on lice waste - ants carry them from one plant to another and help the lice spread. This should be taken into account when checking for almond lice. One female lice gives birth to 70-90 larvae. Females live a month or two. In mid-April, winged lice are born, which begin to damage the buds and young leaves. Peach lice can produce up to 16 offspring a year. Lice give birth to live larvae without laying eggs in the summer. Winged lice begin to appear in May. Lice feed by sucking plant sap from almond leaves as well as growth points. As a result, almonds cause great damage to growth, development and its yield. It also spreads viral diseases found in almonds. The length of the wingless bit is 1.4-2.1 mm, while that of the winged bit is 1.2-1.8 mm. Lice parasites and predators can significantly affect the rate of increase and decrease of lice. However, research in this area has shown that parasites and predators cannot affect the future number of lice change system without human intervention (i.e., biological control of lice) because the natural neighbors of peach lice increase or decrease only after the lice have increased or decreased. Eggs laid by winged lice in late autumn go into winter. A. According to the recommendations of Pulatov [5,6], agro-technical, chemical and biological measures to control peach lice in fruit crops have been identified. Among the agro-technical measures it is recommended to carry out high-quality intercropping, leaf feeding of young seedlings, weed control, biological control of 3-4-day-old eggs of golden-eyed in the ratio 1:10 - 1:20 5 times in 5 days. It has

been stated that chemicals should be applied when 8-10% of the plant's leaf blades are covered with 5-25% of plant lice. Sh. T. Khodjaev [4] in the fight against peach lice in orchards, including almonds, detsis, 2.5% em.k. (0.7 l / ha), Nurell-D, 55% k.em. (1.0 l / ha), fastak, 10% sus.k. (0.3 l / ha) and pirimor, 40% k.em. (2.0 kg / ha). According to many scientists, weeds that grow inside, around, and around the almond grove are the primary staple food for pests. Especially plant lice grow en masse in weeds. Therefore, many researchers have stated that with the emergence of pests in the weeds around the field, their chemical treatment dramatically reduced the number of pests in the main crop areas, thereby creating favorable conditions for tree growth [7]. Many scientists recommend chemical insecticides against peach lice, such as orten 75, acetate 75, phosphorus, siodan, pravado, lannet, fulfull, aktara. The role of entomophages in reducing the quantitative number of pest populations in agricultural areas is immeasurable. As entomophagous and acariphagous, representatives of insects such as auricles, semi-amphibians, thrips, beetles, flies, parasites and amphibians are of practical importance. The role of natural entomophages in reducing pests in almonds is immense. Natural cousins directly reduce most pests in almond agrobiocenosis. The widespread and widespread use of synthetic insecticides causes new problems in the organization of plant protection - the adaptation of pests to pesticides, the negative impact on biodiversity, the violation of biological balance and a number of other problems. Therefore, it is important to find alternative ways to reduce the population

of pests in arable lands. Of course, this leads to such important directions as the use of toxic chemicals, the reduction of their consumption per hectare and the creation of new modern pesticides.

Conclusion. The harmful effects of peach lice on the growth, development and yield of almonds are multifaceted and require a

coordinated protective fight against them. Effective and rational control of lice in orchards is an important measure to increase its growth, development, productivity and quality of raw materials, and serves as an important factor determining the economic efficiency of the industry.

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